

CEreals **RE**siliency **RE**volution for agile
supply chain management in the Mediterranean

D2.3

Analysis of resilient cereal species and agricultural practices for resilient farming

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Executive summary

The CERERE (CEreals REsiliency REvolution for agile supply chain management in the Mediterranean) project under the PRIMA Programme 2023 aims at enhancing the resilience of the agri-food supply chain in the Mediterranean region.

Based on the technical proposal, this deliverable belongs to Task 2.2, which aims to provide the basic agronomic knowledge on the three cereal species (durum wheat, bread wheat and barley) in terms of adaptability to a particular environment/threat/stressor, especially to semi-arid environments, like MENA countries, and the good agricultural practices necessary to represent the ground truth of the resilient farming system. In particular, the best-performing varieties/landraces for each species are inspected, by considering a specific environment/year or a combination of different environments. Together with this information, the analysis of meteorological data retrieved from MENA regions in a long period (2014-2022), together with those from Italian regions whose climate conditions are very similar to those of the MENA regions, has been carried out according to a very long period of thirty years. These data could be helpful to put in relation to climate conditions and production. Finally, the list of good agricultural practices (GAPs) will be given as recommendations, especially for countries like Egypt and Turkey, characterised by a more structured agriculture than other MENA countries.

1. Introduction

The deliverable D2.3 focuses on providing information on the best-performing cereal varieties (bread wheat, durum wheat and barley) cultivated in the MENA regions and the good agricultural practices necessary to represent the ground truth of a resilient farming system. Data available from historical trials, as well as scientific literature, have been used. Wheat and barley cultivars are assessed in terms of adaptability to a particular environment/threat/stressor, with a particular focus on biotic and abiotic stresses, strongly impacting the yield and quality of cereals. The deliverable D2.3 is a report on the best varieties, according to data reported in the database (D2.4), in terms of disease resistance, quality and yield, out of which 10 durum wheat and ten bread wheat genotypes will be selected for the experimental trial in the WP6, when the IoT sensors for data collection from WP4 will also be used. All this data will be the foundation for teams developing machine learning models, disruption analysis, and other decision-making processes (WP3, WP5). The purpose will be to predict crop health, growth trends, or potential yield losses in case of any disruptions or identify correlations between sensed parameters and production anomalies, enabling proactive responses to disease outbreaks or resource deficits.

The analysis of meteorological data from MENA countries and Italian regions of the Middle and South, whose conditions are very similar to those of the Mediterranean area, has been carried out, considering a very long period, to correlate environments and production. In fact, as is known, low rainfall and high temperatures are the main limiting factors in agriculture, and they are indeed included in the list of disruptions within WP3. Therefore, a better understanding of the agro-climatic characteristics of these areas is desirable, if not essential, to optimise agricultural practices, improve yields and mitigate the effects of climate change.

Finally, the report also includes a list of GAPs (Good Agriculture practices) for Egypt and Turkey, characterised by a more structured agriculture than the other countries of the Mediterranean area, that represents a very valuable resource for giving recommendations for farmers and small-holders in those countries.

2. Research Methodology

The scientific literature analysis was carried out to systematically examine existing research relevant to cereal varieties (bread wheat, durum wheat and barley) in MENA countries and in Central-Southern Italy in terms of resistance to fungal diseases, yield production and quality, with the objective to identify how many as possible details on varieties or landraces with a good performance in a specific environment or combination of different environments/years.

The research focused on varieties/landraces actually grown in the environments of the MENA countries and the Mediterranean area, regardless of country of origin. The Mediterranean area and the MENA region are geographically distinct but interrelated. The Mediterranean area refers to the region around the Mediterranean Sea, including the coasts of Europe, Africa and Asia. The MENA region extends from Mauritania (west) to Iran (south-east Asia), including North Africa and the Middle East. So, the Mediterranean area is a larger geographical

region that also includes the MENA region, which focuses mainly on the eastern and northwestern part of the Mediterranean area.

The data collected in our research concern some countries in the Mediterranean area (Italy, Spain, Greece, Portugal and Thrace region) and almost all countries in the MENA region (Turkey, Egypt, Iran, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Algeria, Morocco, Iraq, Tunisia, Lebanon, Jordan and Tunisia).

Each variety/landrace has been analyzed, according to specific parameters, in terms of agronomic trait, resistance disease, yield and quality (as reported and detailed in the database D2.4), while in this report only the best-performing ones are reported and described.

A structured and comprehensive literature search was based on published articles and book chapters and was conducted using the following academic databases: Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, Scientific Journals. Only references for which complete data or valuable information have been used for the database.

The historical data for durum and bread wheat were retrieved from the *Informatore Agrario* (special issues), an Italian magazine, covering a period from 2011 to 2024. For bread wheat data on 166 cultivars with the year of release from 1992 to 2018, classified as 21 biscuit wheat, 17 strength wheat, 90 bread wheat, 35 superior bread wheat and two waxy, were retrieved, with trials from 56 different locations widespread across Italy. On the other hand, for durum wheat, we found data for 255 cultivars with the year of release from 1974 to 2020, covering 8 geographic areas across Italy. In both cases, grain yield is available for each genotype in each location/year combination, whereas for the other traits related to plant morphology (plant height), phenology (heading date), grain quality (test weight, thousand kernel weight, etc.) and reaction to some fungal diseases following natural infection in field, are available as average from a set of locations in the North, Centre and South of Italy.

The meteorological data for Center and South Italy were retrieved from the ISPRA (Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research) website (www.isprambiente.gov.it). Since January 14 2017, ISPRA, together with 21 Agencies, both at the regional level (ARPA) and provincial level (APPA), represent the SNPA - *Sistema Nazionale a rete per la Protezione dell'Ambiente* (National Network System for Environmental Protection), established by Law n. 132 of June 28 2016. ISPRA uses the database of the SCIA system - *Sistema Nazionale per la raccolta, elaborazione e diffusione di Dati Climatici di Interesse Ambientale* (National System for the collection, processing and dissemination of Climate Data of Environmental Interest, www.scia.isprambiente.it). For climate characterisation, both at the regional level (single region) and the entire territorial level (Central and Southern Italy) level, the Normal Climatic Values (NCV) of two parameters were taken into consideration: rain and temperature. For climate variables, NCV represents an average value that derives from a sufficiently long reference period. For a coherent and standardised comparison of the information from different global meteorological services, the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) has imposed the use of the NCV by setting the duration of the reference period at 30 years, which terminates with zero, with an update of the period every 10 years. Normal Climatic Values are used as reference values to compare the observations, calculate the series of anomalies (deviations from normal values) and provide average values representative of the current or recent past climate in a specific location/area. For the calculation of the NCV, the daily data are the starting point from which to derive the monthly values (as an average, sum or number of days above or below a threshold value, and so on) and, therefore, the Normal Climatic Value is the average value calculated over the thirty-year

climatological period, considering only the values of the weather stations with at least 24 years of valid and complete data. Based on the NCV, seasonal and annual normal values are also calculated. Based on the complete NCV series of the 1991-2020 period, the Central and Southern Italy (CSI) climate characterisation, both for each region and for the entire territory, has been carried out considering the following parameters: rainfall and temperature.

The meteorological data for MENA countries, instead, were retrieved from the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) website, covering a period from 2014 to 2022 (<https://aquastat.fao.org/climate-information-tool/>).

3. Description and analysis of climate variables in MENA regions and Italy

3.1 Climate characterisation of MENA regions

The Middle East and North Africa (MENA) regions are characterised by diverse and climatically challenging areas, including arid, semi-arid and Mediterranean environments. Despite these heavy limitations, cereal cultivations, particularly wheat and barley, represent a pivotal key to both regional food security and rural livelihoods in these countries. Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Syria, Iraq and parts of Iran are countries in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), characterised by mild, wet winters and hot, dry summers, where cereal production mainly occurs. In general, rainfall shows a typical seasonal trend, concentrated between November and March, a notable interannual variability and annual rainfall between 200 and 600 mm. It is well known that most cereal farms in the MENA region do not have the possibility, especially during the cereal grain ripening stage, to intervene with irrigation to replace the severe rainfall deficit. Therefore, the rainfall pattern is indeed a critical factor for cereal crops, as even a small shift in the onset, intensity or duration of the rainy season can have a substantial impact on crop yields. In particular, the cereal-growing areas spread across the western part of the region, such as Morocco and Algeria, are mostly located in the coastal plains and foothills of the Atlas Mountains and benefit from relatively higher rainfall than the inland and southern areas. However, prolonged periods of drought linked to a high risk of desertification due to irregular rainfall are increasingly frequent. In the eastern parts of the region, including Syria, Iraq and parts of Iran, winter rainfall is often very heavy but due to climate variability and the vulnerability of continentality, the problem of rainfall deficiency is also very critical here. In addition to the phenomenon of irregular and low rainfall, temperature is also a very important factor affecting grain yield in the MENA region, especially the high temperatures recorded in late spring and early summer during the growing season. In cereal-growing areas, average daytime temperatures can vary from 15 °C to 25 °C, even exceeding 30 °C during the grain filling phase, temperature levels that can negatively impact yields. Due to evident climate changes, this risk could be even more serious when considering the increased frequency of heat waves. The combination of both factors, low rainfall and high temperature during the cereal growing season, turns into high

evapotranspiration rates and limited soil moisture retention, making cereal crops particularly sensitive to water stress. In conclusion, a deeper understanding of these key climate parameters is essential for the development of resilient agricultural policies and practices focused on preserving and sustaining cereal production in the MENA regions. Based on the period 2014-2022, the area cultivated with cereals in the MENA region is reported in decreasing order (Table 1) (<https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>). The 35% of the cultivated area is located mainly in the Iran region, followed by Morocco (17%), Egypt (12%), Algeria (11%), Syria (10%) and, to a lesser extent than 10% of the total area, by Iraq, Tunisia, Libya and Saudi Arabia.

Precipitation and temperature (min-max-mean) parameters were used for the climate characterisation of MENA regions, considering the same period from 2014 to 2022 (<https://aquastat.fao.org/climate-information-tool/>). For each MENA region, annual and monthly average data of precipitation and temperature were grouped and reported in Tables 2-3-4-5. A detail of each climate trait was elaborated by CREA to describe their trend in the three main periods of the cereal growing season.

Table 1_Total area under cereal cultivation in MENA countries in the 2014-2022 (Source of data: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>)

Country Code	MENAREGION COUNTRIES	Land under cereal cultivation (hectares). Cereals include wheat, rice, maize, barley, oats, rye, millet, sorghum, buckwheat, and mixed grains										Period Average (2014-2022)	% of Total
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022			
IRN	Iran, Islamic Rep.	8555401	8182763	8449886	8800337	9081051	11094432	9454460	9073243	8107539	8977679	35%	
MAR	Morocco	4769853	5459896	3804119	5569212	4590740	3657072	4449871	4487822	3720619	4501023	17%	
EGY	Egypt, Arab Rep.	3291950	3251394	3224925	3097555	2592349	3623430	3134051	3146954	3226804	3176601	12%	
DZA	Algeria	2509193	2686241	3376449	3512157	3107776	3187485	2889582	1941867	2929807	2904506	11%	
SYR	Syrian Arab Republic	2534198	2300226	2400266	2379322	2312042	2884101	2904822	3065229	2396243	2575161	10%	
IRQ	Iraq	3441479	1288713	1303200	1359359	977375	2673021	3440808	1942488	1179042	1956165	8%	
TUN	Tunisia	1301380	1214999	859541	1255987	1180600	1246430	1181471	1156488	1044557	1160161	4%	
LBY	Libya	456480	382691	446754	309919	410781	328368	313169	313368	313402	363881	1%	
SAU	Saudi Arabia	302139	289608	277005	265312	245988	244295	259567	185646	213661	253691	1%	
JOR	Jordan	61768	61812	54334	47410	55112	68862	61457	66941	55039	59193	0%	
LBN	Lebanon	52164	55104	57418	57565	55260	56260	56280	61272	55229	56284	0%	
OMN	Oman	5247	5646	4889	4894	4846	4882	9778	6771	8420	6153	0%	
KWT	Kuwait	2453	1423	1007	1079	1070	1781	2009	1982	1972	1642	0%	
ARE	United Arab Emirates	181	105	179	557	392	1094	1391	1185	975	673	0%	
QAT	Qatar	378	308	293	275	265	153	211	392	289	285	0%	
DJ	Djibouti	8	9	8	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	0%	
Total hecaters		27284272	25180938	24260273	26660948	24615655	29071675	28158936	25451657	23253607	25993107		

Table 2_ Annual and monthly precipitation (2014-2022 average) in MENA regions and rainfall distribution in the three main periods of the cereal growing season.

MENA Regions	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Annual	CGS	
	Rainfall (mm)														
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer					
Iran, Islamic Rep.	0	14	87	70	48	32	43	28	4	0	1	1	327	318	
Morocco	14	49	70	67	65	45	66	58	24	7	1	1	466	427	
Egypt, Arab Rep.	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	3	
Algeria	0	2	3	3	2	2	0	1	4	0	3	2	22	17	
Syrian Arab Republic	73	45	59	27	15	6	1	1	4	22	37	72	361	175	
Iraq	69	68	86	40	11	1	0	0	1	31	63	93	461	235	
Tunisia	12	22	50	21	13	7	2	20	37	33	20	19	256	205	
Libya	60	26	18	3	2	1	1	1	5	16	19	55	207	69	
Saudi Arabia	7	7	6	14	2	0	0	0	0	1	26	18	81	40	
Rainfall average	26	26	42	27	18	10	13	12	9	12	19	29	243	165	
Average vs .Total rainfall (%)	11	11	17	11	7	4	5	5	4	5	8	12			
Seasonal rainfall distribution (%)	39			23			14			25					
Cereal Growing Season (CGS; Mid October-Mid July)	165														
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)	110														
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-Mid May)							29								
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (Mid May/June-July)										26					

Table 3_ Annual and monthly average temperature (2014-2022 average) in MENA regions and its values during the three main periods of the cereal growing season.

MENA Regions	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Annual	CGS	
	Tmean (°C)														
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer					
Iran, Islamic Rep.	34,4	28,2	19,6	14,2	12,4	14,8	19,6	25,8	31,8	32,5	35,6	37,3	25,5	23,5	
Morocco	25,5	23,2	17,4	14,6	12,8	14,2	15,6	18,2	22,5	24,6	27,4	27,9	20,3	19,0	
Egypt, Arab Rep.	11,7	13,9	17,7	22,3	26,9	29,1	29,7	30,1	28,0	24,0	18,5	14,0	22,2	24,0	
Algeria	12,9	16,0	18,9	25,0	29,9	33,9	36,1	35,5	32,7	25,9	18,6	14,5	25,0	27,3	
Syrian Arab Republic	6,9	9,1	12,3	17,6	22,8	26,4	29,5	29,6	26,8	21,5	14,1	9,1	18,8	21,0	
Iraq	8,8	10,6	14,5	20,2	26,9	32,4	35,9	35,8	31,5	25,1	16,3	11,0	22,4	24,9	
Tunisia	12,2	13,6	14,9	18,5	23,0	27,7	30,5	30,3	27,2	22,2	17,4	13,5	20,9	22,5	
Libya	15,2	15,0	15,7	18,0	20,5	23,2	25,4	26,5	25,8	23,7	20,5	17,1	20,6	21,4	
Saudi Arabia	13,2	15,3	20,6	25,0	30,4	33,4	34,9	34,6	32,2	27,0	19,4	14,6	25,0	27,3	
Tmean average	15,6	16,1	16,8	19,5	22,8	26,1	28,6	29,6	28,7	25,2	20,9	17,7	22,3	23,4	
Seasonal Tmean (°C)	16,2			22,8			29,0			21,2					
Cereal Growing Season (CGS)	23,4														
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)	20,3														
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-May)							29,0								
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (May/June-July)										23,0					

Table 4_ Annual and monthly maximum temperature (2014-2022 average) in MENA regions and its values during the three main periods of the cereal growing season.

MENA Regions	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Annual	CGS	
	Tmax (°C)														
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer					
Iran, Islamic Rep.	43,3	36,2	25,4	19,2	17,8	20,8	26,2	33,1	40,6	46,0	47,6	47,0	33,6	31,3	
Morocco	32,1	29,8	22,8	19,7	18,0	19,9	21,6	24,6	30,1	32,0	35,4	35,5	26,8	25,4	
Egypt, Arab Rep.	17,3	19,9	24,3	29,5	33,9	35,8	36,1	36,3	34,1	29,8	24,0	19,3	28,4	30,4	
Algeria	19,8	23,0	26,1	32,5	37,0	41,1	42,9	42,1	39,4	32,5	25,0	20,9	31,9	34,2	
Syrian Arab Republic	11,1	14,1	17,5	23,9	29,4	33,0	36,6	36,5	33,4	27,4	19,2	13,2	24,6	27,1	
Iraq	13,3	15,6	19,8	26,5	33,6	39,6	43,1	42,9	38,5	31,0	21,3	15,4	28,4	31,2	
Tunisia	18,2	20,0	21,2	25,4	30,3	35,4	38,2	37,5	33,4	28,0	23,1	19,0	27,5	29,3	
Libya	16,7	16,7	17,4	19,7	21,9	24,3	26,1	27,3	27,0	25,1	22,1	18,6	21,9	22,8	
Saudi Arabia	19,6	22,2	27,7	32,3	37,6	40,9	42,2	41,9	39,7	34,2	25,4	20,4	32,0	34,4	
Tmax average	21,3	22,0	22,5	25,4	28,9	32,3	34,8	35,8	35,1	31,8	27,0	23,2	28,3	29,6	
Seasonal Tmax (°C)	21,9			28,9			35,2			27,4					
Cereal Growing Season (CGS)													29,6		
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)			26,2												
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-May)							35,2								
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (May/June-July)										29,4					

Table 5_ Annual and monthly minimum temperature (2014-2022 average) in MENA regions and its values during the three main periods of the cereal growing season.

MENA Regions	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Annual	CGS	
	Tmin (°C)														
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer					
Iran, Islamic Rep.	25,4	20,3	13,8	9,1	7,1	8,9	13,0	18,4	23,0	19,1	23,6	27,6	17,4	15,6	
Morocco	18,8	16,6	12,0	9,5	7,5	8,5	9,5	11,8	14,9	17,1	19,4	20,2	13,8	12,7	
Egypt, Arab Rep.	6,1	7,8	11,2	15,1	19,9	22,4	23,3	23,9	21,9	18,2	13,1	8,8	16,0	17,7	
Algeria	6,0	9,0	11,6	17,6	22,8	26,7	29,2	29,0	26,1	19,4	12,0	8,0	18,1	20,3	
Syrian Arab Republic	2,8	4,1	7,1	11,4	16,2	19,7	22,4	22,7	20,3	15,5	9,0	5,0	13,0	14,8	
Iraq	4,3	5,6	9,2	13,9	20,1	25,3	28,8	28,6	24,5	19,1	11,4	6,6	16,5	18,7	
Tunisia	6,2	7,2	8,6	11,6	15,6	19,9	22,7	23,1	20,9	16,4	11,8	8,0	14,4	15,8	
Libya	13,7	13,4	13,9	16,2	19,0	22,2	24,6	25,7	24,6	22,3	19,0	15,7	19,2	20,1	
Saudi Arabia	6,7	8,4	13,4	17,7	23,2	25,8	27,6	27,3	24,6	19,7	13,4	8,9	18,1	20,1	
Tmin average	10,0	10,3	11,2	13,6	16,8	19,9	22,4	23,4	22,3	18,5	14,7	12,1	16,3	17,3	
Seasonal Tmin (°C)	10,5			16,8			22,7			15,1					
Cereal Growing Season (CGS)													17,3		
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)			14,4												
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-May)							22,7								
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (May/June-July)										16,6					

Following is the Figure 1 showing the summary of the trend of precipitation, average temperatures and thermal delta (Tmax – Tmin) for each region of the MENA considered in our analysis.

Figure 1_ Average annual trend of cumulative precipitation and temperatures (mean and thermal delta). The average values are the average of the period 2014-2022.

Overall, over the period 2014-2022, the regions Morocco, Syria and Iraq show a favourable climate trend, with cumulative annual precipitation above the average temperature, although the thermal delta is quite high but generally lower than in other regions, except for Libya. Egypt, Algeria and Saudi Arabia are the regions with very little or absent rains.

From an agronomic point of view, it is more important to observe the overall trend of these two climate parameters during the cereal growing season in the MENA regions, considered from October to mid-July (Figure 2). December is the month with the highest rainfall (around 45 mm), after which the trend decreases until March, remaining constant until June (around 10 mm), and then rising again until September (around 30 mm). Therefore, the critical period of water deficiency for cereal cultivation in the MENA regions starts in February-March and lasts until June, a period during which the average temperature and the thermal delta also increase, favoring the phenomenon of evapotranspiration and drought stress for plants. This undesirable combination results in a decrease in wheat yield, since the increase in temperature above 28 °C from April to June can cause flower abortion and a strong shrinkage of the kernels during the grain ripening stage. Figure 3 shows the above situation of each country in the MENA region elaborated by CREA.

Figure 2_ Average monthly trend of cumulative precipitation and temperatures (mean and thermal delta). The average values are the average of the period 2014-2022.

Figure 3_ Average monthly trend of cumulative precipitation and temperatures (mean and thermal delta) for each country of MENA, considered in the analysis. The average values are for the period 2014-2022.

3.2 Climatic characterisation of Central-Southern Italian regions

Landscapes, agricultural traditions and climate conditions individually characterise Central and Southern Italy. In general, Central and Southern Italy show a predominantly Mediterranean climate. The main agronomic and climatic information of these regions of Italy are here described.

Lazio

- Agronomic features: fertile volcanic soils, especially in the areas near Rome and Viterbo, which favor the cultivation of cereals, olives and grapes (production of renowned wines such as Frascati and Cesanese). The coastal plain is rich in horticultural crops and the famous Roman artichoke.
- Climate features: along the coast, the climate is typically Mediterranean, with warm and dry summers and mild, wet winters. Inland, instead, is a mix of Mediterranean and semi-continental conditions, with cooler winters due to higher altitudes.

Abruzzo

- Agronomic features: a marked diversity characterises the agricultural landscape of Abruzzo. Wheat, olives, and grapes (area of Montepulciano d' Abruzzo wines) are the predominant crops on the plains and along the coast. Sheep farming, important for cheese production (typically Pecorino), is mainly developed in the Apennine mountains.
- Climate features: the coastal areas show a Mediterranean climate that contrasts with the more rigid and continental conditions, with significant snowfall in winter, of the mountainous areas.

Molise

- Agronomic features: small-scale agriculture represents this region based mainly on crops such as wheat, maize, olives, and wine grapes and on sheep and cattle livestock farming developed in the mountainous areas.
- Climate features: similarly to Abruzzo, the Molise region also shows a transitional climate where the Mediterranean climate excels on the coast while the inland areas suffer colder winters and cooler summers due to higher elevations.

Campania

- Agronomy features: the volcanic soils of this region around Mount Vesuvius promote a rich agricultural output based on the famous production of tomatoes (San Marzano), citrus fruits, and hazelnuts but also wines (like Taurasi).
- Climate features: the region shows a predominantly Mediterranean climate, with mild, wet winters and hot, dry summers, while moderate temperatures are present in the coastal areas.

Puglia

- Agronomy features: large agricultural extension of Italy known for being the first region in the production of olives and olive oil but also in the production of durum wheat for pasta, table grapes, almonds, and tomatoes.

- Climate features: typically, the Mediterranean climate characterised by hot, dry summers and mild winters. During the winter months, the most rainfall is concentrated, contributing to a semi-arid environment in some areas.

Basilicata

- Agronomy features: although Basilicata's rugged terrain limits large-scale farming, there is small-scale agriculture based on wheat, olives, and grapes (high-quality Aglianico del Vulture wine) along with interesting sheep and goat farming.
- Climate features: region characterised by a Mediterranean climate along the coast and colder winters and cooler summers in the mountains. The low annual rainfall present in some areas leads to semi-arid conditions.

Calabria

- Agronomy features: olive groves, citrus orchards (notably bergamot), and vineyards, producing local wines (like Cirò), as well as fig and pomegranate orchards, are the main crops of this region.
- Climate features: the Mediterranean climate characterises the coastal areas, while the cooler, more temperate climate prevails in the inland mountains. Higher rainfall favors the Aspromonte area compared to the coastal plains.

Sicily

- Agronomy features: the fertile volcanic soils are mainly grown by wheat, olives, almonds, and citrus fruits (oranges and lemons). In addition, the wines produced in this region are known for their high quality (Nero d'Avola and Marsala).
- Climate features: hot and dry summers and mild and wet winters are expressions of the Mediterranean climate, while higher temperature extremes can occur in the inland areas.

Sardinia

- Agronomy features: a diversified and less intensive agricultural compared to mainland regions, is dedicated to the production of cork, olive oil, sheep's milk (pecorino cheese), and high-quality wines (Vermentino and Cannonau).
- Climate features: on the regional coasts the climate is Mediterranean, with arid summers and mild winters, while the interior areas are influenced by the continental, with significant diurnal temperature variation.

Marche

- Agronomy features: a diversified agricultural landscape is dedicated to the production of cereal crops (durum wheat, barley and corn), vegetables, fruits (apples, cherries, peaches) and wine (Verdicchio, Rosso Conero).
- Climate features: Mediterranean along the coast, more continental inland. Winters are mild, and summers are hot and humid.

Tuscany

- Agronomy features: a fertile environment for a diverse range of agricultural products like vineyards, olive groves, and cereal crops. The region is known also for various fruits, vegetables, and livestock, making it a rich agricultural landscape. To highlight its wine production, particularly the Chianti region near Siena.

- Climate features: generally mild, Mediterranean climate with four distinct seasons. Summers are hot and dry, while winters are mild and wet. Spring and autumn offer pleasant, milder weather with less rainfall.

Umbria

- Agronomy features: there is a variety of crops, including wheat, corn, sunflower and forage, as well as olive oil from organic olives. The region is also known for its tobacco, wine and traditional food products such as pork, pastries and pasta.
- Climate features: is generally mild by a Mediterranean influence, transitioning to a more continental climate in the inland areas. Winters are cold and rainy, with frequent frosts and occasional snow. Springs and autumns are the wettest seasons, but relatively mild. Summers are hot and dry.

Lazio, Marche, Tuscany and Umbria are regions belonging to Central Italy, while South Italy includes Abruzzo, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Molise and Puglia; the islands are Sardinia and Sicily.

The sum of the monthly and annual rainfall was considered for each region and overall area of CSI. These values were also divided considering the orographic level of territory, such as plain, hill, and mountain, and grouped into three-month periods relating to winter, spring, summer, and autumn seasons. Finally, as regards the durum wheat crop, the total rainfall of the season growing (October-June/July) was divided into three periods: the first, from sowing to until to the complete tillering stage (October-February); the second, from elongation to the heading/starting of grain ripening stage (March-May), and, the third, from grain ripening to maturation stage (May/June-July, °C). In addition to the amount of rain, it was also interesting to evaluate another aspect for each rain event: the smallest amount of rain that can be considered agronomically useful. Generally, this entity is set to at least 5 mm of continuous rain and therefore, it is also important to know the number of days in one month with rain values greater than or equal to 5 mm.

Also, for each region and overall area of CSI, the monthly and annual averages of the minimum and maximum temperatures were elaborated by CREA; an analysis like that performed for rainfall was carried out for these parameters.

Figure 4 shows the annual rainfall and the total number of meteorological stations present in the territory and by altitude of Central-Southern Italy (CSI). The bars of the annual rainfall show that the precipitation increases progressively with increasing altitude and that, on average, the annual rainfall is 847 mm over the entire CSI territory.

Figure 4_Annual rainfall distribution in entire territory of Central-Southern Italy.

Figure 5 shows the distribution of annual rainfall both by region and by altitude within each region. At the regional level, Tuscany and Calabria record precipitations above 1000 mm, Puglia and the two islands show precipitations of about 700 mm and the remaining regions of about 900 mm. The flat areas of the CSI territory have a less variable precipitation pattern than the hilly and mountainous areas.

Figure 5_Annual rainfall distribution for each region

Table 6 shows the rainfall distribution by month, by climatic seasonal and cereal growing season. In autumn and winter, concentrates account for 65% of the total precipitations, with November and December being the wettest months. About 25% of the rainfall is equally distributed in the spring months, and the remaining part of rainfall during the summer.

Table 6_ Monthly and seasonal rainfall distribution

Central-Southern Italian Regions	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	CGS
	Rainfall (mm)												
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer			
Tuscany	101	143	175	134	99	96	94	89	82	60	37	48	920
Marche	94	93	119	101	67	72	81	87	80	64	47	51	741
Lazio	77	104	132	101	68	70	69	65	59	31	22	29	658
Abruzzo	70	78	105	92	71	60	71	79	74	51	47	42	665
Puglia	64	73	88	76	69	55	64	51	41	31	25	28	523
Campania	78	93	145	98	86	71	72	68	46	24	16	24	665
Calabria	89	109	144	144	128	110	103	66	46	26	22	28	833
Sicily	62	80	84	95	91	74	67	49	27	16	8	17	546
Sardinia	50	66	115	97	73	61	58	66	48	21	8	16	576
Rainfall average	76	93	123	104	84	74	75	69	56	36	26	31	
Average vs. Total rainfall (%)	9	11	15	12	10	9	9	8	7	4	3	4	
Seasonal rainfall distribution (%)	34			31			24			11			
Cereal Growing Season (CGS; Mid October-Mid July)	681												
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)	432												
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-Mid May)							172						
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (Mid May/June-July)										77			

For the cereal growing season, although 681 mm of rainfall is sufficient to cover the water requirements of a cereal crop, only a third is available during the critical stage of grain maturation and may not be appropriate to compensate for the high levels of evapotranspiration present during this period. Among the CSI regions, Puglia, Sicily and Sardinia are the most at-risk regarding the water supply of cereal cultivation since rainfall during growing season is less than 600 mm. For a better characterisation of the CSI territory, in addition to the annual rainfall, it is interesting to know how much rain is agronomically useful, i.e. for each rain event, how much exceeds the threshold of 5 mm of continuous rainfall.

Figure 6 shows the distribution of days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm both for the entire CSI territory and for altitude. During the year, on average, only 46 days present events with rainfall ≥ 5 mm decreasing from 56 days in the mountains to 41 days in the plain.

Figure 6_Days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm in entire territory of Center and South Italy

Figure 7 shows the distribution of days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm both for the entire CSI territory, at the regional level and by altitude within each region. Sicily, Sardinia and Puglia are the most critical regions since they have the lowest number of days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm.

Figure 7_Days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm for each region

Table 7 shows the distribution of days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm by month, by climatic seasonal, and by cereal growing season is reported. The most critical months result to be May-June-July with respectively only 3-2-1 days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm, corresponding to the grain ripening-maturation phase of the cereal crop. During the cereal growing season, there are, on average 40 days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm distributed in 25 days during the winter season (sowing-full tillering), 12 days during the reproductive phase (elongation-start of grain ripening) and 3 days during the grain maturation phase.

Table 7_Days with distribution rainfall ≥ 5 mm for month and season

Regions of the Center and South Italy	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	CGS
	Days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm (n.) for each month and grouped by season												
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer			
Tuscany	4	6	7	6	5	5	5	5	5	3	2	2	49
Marche	5	5	6	6	4	4	5	5	5	4	3	3	46
Lazio	4	5	7	5	4	4	4	4	4	2	1	1	40
Abruzzo	4	4	6	5	4	4	4	5	4	3	2	2	41
Puglia	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	2	1	2	33
Campania	3	5	8	6	5	5	4	4	3	1	1	1	42
Calabria	4	5	6	7	6	6	5	4	3	1	1	1	44
Sicily	3	4	5	5	5	4	4	3	1	1	0	1	33
Sardinia	3	3	6	5	4	4	4	4	3	1	0	1	34
Average of days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm (n.)	4	5	6	6	5	4	4	4	3	2	1	2	
Seasonal sum of days with rainfall ≥ 5 mm (n.)	14			14			12			5			
Cereal Growing Season (CGS)	40												
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)	25												
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-May)	12												
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (May/June-July)	3												

Figure 8 shows the distribution of the Tmax for both the entire CSI territory and altitude. The maximum temperature of the entire CSI territory is 19.3 °C, ranging from 16.2 °C in the mountains to 20.9 °C in the plains.

Moreover, the distribution of the Tmax both for the entire CSI territory, at the regional level and by altitude within each region is shown in Figure 9. Sicily, Sardinia, Puglia, and Lazio regions have Tmax values above 20.0 °C, with Sicily being the warmest (22.0 °C).

Figure 8_ Average Tmax distribution in the entire territory of Center and South Italy

Figure 9_ Average Tmax for each region

The values of the Tmax by month, by climatic seasonal, and by cereal growing season are described in Table 8. During the cereal growing season, the Tmax is 17.7 °C on average, ranging from 13.8 °C in the winter to 17.7 °C

during the reproductive phase, reaching 27.8 °C in the grain maturation phase. January and August are at the extremes of the year, with Tmax of 10.5 °C and 29.6 °C, respectively.

Table 8_ Monthly and seasonal Tmax for regions of Center and South of Italy

Regions of the Center and South Italy	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	CGS
	Tmax (°C)												
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer			
Tuscany	24,7	19,6	14,3	10,5	9,9	11,1	14,3	17,8	22,1	26,4	29,5	29,7	17,6
Umbria	25,4	20,5	14,6	10,3	10,1	11,8	15,2	18,5	22,8	27,6	30,6	30,9	18,2
Marche	23,6	18,6	13,3	9,3	8,4	9,5	13,1	16,8	21,4	26,0	28,9	29,0	16,5
Abruzzo	22,9	18,6	13,5	9,4	8,5	9,2	12,4	15,9	20,2	24,8	27,8	28,2	16,0
Molise	24,0	19,7	14,7	10,7	9,7	10,1	13,1	16,4	20,9	25,8	28,5	28,9	16,9
Lazio	25,8	21,4	16,4	12,7	11,8	12,7	15,3	18,3	22,6	27,0	29,9	30,4	18,8
Puglia	25,9	21,5	16,7	12,7	11,6	12,4	15,0	18,6	23,4	28,3	31,0	31,0	19,1
Campania	25,1	20,9	16,0	12,0	10,9	11,3	13,9	17,1	21,6	26,0	28,8	29,5	17,9
Basilicata	21,0	17,1	12,0	7,9	6,8	7,4	10,2	13,3	18,1	22,7	25,5	26,1	14,1
Calabria	24,2	20,3	15,6	11,7	10,5	10,9	13,4	16,3	20,9	25,5	28,1	28,6	17,3
Sicily	27,6	23,7	19,1	15,4	14,3	14,4	16,6	19,3	23,6	28,1	31,0	31,4	20,5
Sardinia	26,7	22,8	17,5	14,1	13,2	13,5	16,0	18,8	23,1	27,8	31,0	31,3	19,8
Tmax average (Tmax)	24,7	20,4	15,3	11,4	10,5	11,2	14,0	17,2	21,7	26,3	29,2	29,6	
Seasonal Tmax average (°C)	20,1			11,0			17,7			28,4			
Cereal Growing Season (CGS)	17,7												
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)	13,8												
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-May)	17,7												
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (May/June-July)	27,8												

The same considerations for T max have been made for T min. Figure 10 shows the distribution of the Tmin for both the entire CSI territory and altitude. The minimum temperature of the entire CSI territory is 10.8 °C, ranging from 7.9 °C in the mountains to 12.1 °C in the plains. In Figure 11, the distribution of the Tmin both for the entire CSI territory, at the regional level and by altitude within each region, was reported, with Tuscany, Umbria, Marche and Abruzzo regions having Tmin values below 10.0 °C, and Umbria being the coldest one (8.5 °C).

Figure 10_ Average Tmin distribution in entire territory of the Center and South Italy

Figure 11_ Average Tmin distribution for each region

The minimum temperature distributed by month, by climatic season, and by cereal growing season is reported in Table 9. During the cereal growing season, the Tmin is 9.5 °C on average, ranging from 6.7 °C in the winter to 8.8 °C during the reproductive phase and reaching 17.6 °C in the grain maturation phase. January/February and August are at the extremes of the year, with Tmin of 3.8/3.7 °C and 19.2 °C, respectively.

Table 9 _ Monthly and seasonal Tmin for regions of Center and South of Italy

Regions of the Center and South Italy	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	CGS
	Tmin (°C)												
	Autumn			Winter			Spring			Summer			
Tuscany	14,3	11,1	7,2	3,6	2,7	2,7	5,0	7,7	11,5	15,2	17,5	17,8	8,4
Umbria	13,5	10,1	5,9	2,1	1,0	1,1	3,6	6,2	10,5	14,4	16,6	17,0	7,2
Abruzzo	13,7	10,3	6,4	2,8	1,6	1,6	4,1	7,1	11,1	15,0	17,4	17,7	7,7
Marche	13,8	10,3	6,2	2,4	1,4	1,6	4,3	7,2	11,4	15,4	17,7	17,9	7,8
Lazio	15,9	12,5	8,8	5,2	4,1	4,1	6,2	8,7	12,4	16,3	18,7	19,2	9,7
Molise	16,9	13,3	9,2	5,7	4,5	4,3	6,6	9,4	13,7	18,1	20,7	21,0	10,5
Puglia	16,7	13,1	9,4	5,9	4,7	4,7	6,7	9,4	13,5	17,8	20,3	20,5	10,5
Campania	18,2	14,9	11,0	7,8	6,5	6,3	8,2	10,6	14,4	18,4	20,9	21,5	11,9
Basilicata	14,3	11,2	7,2	3,6	2,4	2,4	4,2	6,7	11,0	15,0	17,4	18,1	8,1
Calabria	16,1	13,0	9,3	6,0	4,7	4,4	6,1	8,5	12,4	16,4	18,9	19,5	10,0
Sicily	18,6	15,6	11,7	8,5	7,0	6,7	8,2	10,4	14,0	17,9	20,5	21,2	12,1
Sardinia	16,0	13,0	9,2	6,2	5,0	4,8	6,5	8,7	12,1	16,0	18,6	19,1	10,0
Tmin average (°C)	15,7	12,4	8,5	5,0	3,8	3,7	5,8	8,4	12,3	16,3	18,8	19,2	
Seasonal Tmin average (°C)	12,2			4,2			8,8			18,1			
Cereal Growing Season (CGS)	9,5												
Sowing-Complete tillering stage (October-February)	6,7												
Elongation-Earing/Start of the grain ripening stage (March-May)							8,8						
Grain ripening-Maturation stage (May/June-July)							17,6						

4. Analysis of resilient cereal varieties

4.1 Durum wheat

Durum wheat is economically and nutritionally important to produce cous cous and pasta products. Abiotic and biotic stresses are significantly impacting yield and quality in many countries around the Mediterranean basin. The research in literature for different agronomic traits and yield production in durum wheat cultivated in MENA regions resulted in 18,530 entries, including landraces and cultivars (D2.4). Even if it is known from the literature that landraces have lower production, despite their superiority in terms of disease resistance than modern varieties, in our meta-analysis, we found no data on grain yield for landraces. In contrast, production is available for varieties in different environments. Yield ranged from 11,97 t/ha for Daurur in North Italy (2017) to 0,1 t/ha for some varieties, such as Platani and Pietrafitta, in a particular environment/year (Musghar, Jordan, 2018). Interestingly, other two varieties were found to have yield values over 10 t/ha in a specific Italian environment: Liberdur (Agugliano, AN, 2012) and Dylan (Fiorenzuola d'Arda, PC, 2012) (L'informatore agrario 2012, 2017). Generally, yield was higher in regions where high precipitation occurred and lower in arid or semi-arid regions.

Nevertheless, the cv Beltorax, analyzed in sixteen Italian environments spread in the South of Italy in 2020, characterised by scarce rain and high temperature, especially during the summer, showed a production ranging from 8,75 to 2,29 t/ha. The cv Biensur from trials spread in the middle and northern Italy, typically characterised by lower temperatures and higher rainfall, across the years 2011-2012-2013, also has a good production (maximum 9,57 t/ha and minimum 3,09, both in central Italy). Cultivars for which high-yield productions or in any case not lower than 3 t/ha in different Italian environments were Adamello, Ampsicora, Dauno III, Garigliano, Grifoni 235, PR22D89, Preco, Redidenari, and Shardana, evaluated in the South of Italy, and Adone, Arnacoris, Cesare, Fabulis, Karur, PR22D40, RGT Rangodur, Serafo Nick and Texur, from the evaluation in the central/northern part of Italy.

Giving a look at other Mediterranean areas, among Egyptian varieties, Benisweif 8 had a mean production of 3,1 t/ha when evaluated at the Sids location during the years 2019-2020, whereas the Turkish cultivars Ç – 1252, Dumlupinar, Kızıltan-9 and Umrabi, evaluated in two locations in Iraq and Turkey, both in 2015, showed a mean yield of 3,5 t/ha. The Mexican/Iranian cultivars Imren, Saji and Zahab, evaluated in Iran during the two consecutive years, 2017 and 2018, showed a mean value of 4,5 t/ha. Moreover, the Algerian cultivar Waha was evaluated in Morocco at different locations during two consecutive growing seasons (2014-2015) and showed a promising yield (7,3 t/ha at Sidi Allal Tazi, 2014), even if a lower value was observed at Jemhâa Shaim in the same year (1,7 t/ha) when scarce precipitation was registered. Finally, good production was obtained for the CYMMIT78 and CYMMIT73 lines evaluated in Lebanon and Morocco in 2015 and 2016, with higher values registered in 2015 in both cases (up to 8 t/ha).

When Thousand kernel weight (TKW) was considered as a parameter strongly correlated to yield production, the range in grams was from 40 for the cv Normanno, representing the mean value from different environments of Southern Italy in 2012, to 85 in the case of the cv Furio Camillo as mean data from several environments of Central Italy. Generally, taking into account varieties for which a high number of data are available from different environments, very good values, never lower than 40 g, were found for the cultivars Emilio Lepido, Idefix, Imhotep, K26, Marco Aurelio, Mario, Monastir, Obelix, Pietrafitta, PR22D89, Prospero, RGT Anvergur, San Carlo, Santo Graal, Spartaco, and SY Leonardo. sMassimo Meridio and Simeto are very promising, with a mean value of 53 g and 51 g, respectively, analysed in a wide range of environments during six consecutive years (2012-2017). Interesting results were also found for the cv Mohawk (50 g), Monsanto Agricultura España (56 g), Razzak (64 g) and Senadur (56 g) evaluated in Lebanon and Morocco in 2015. Finally, cultivars Benisweif 7, Benisweif 8 and Sohag 4 resulted in a medium-high TKW (50 g) when cultivated in Egypt, even if their grain yield production is low.

Another important trait strongly influencing yield production is the response to diseases. Disease-resistant cultivars provide one of the best ways to control them. Data on disease resistance is not available for all varieties included in the literature search. Fungal diseases for which a reaction (resistant or susceptible) or a disease severity was identified include tan spot (caused by *Pyrenophora tritici repentis*), rusts (stem, leaf and stripe rusts, caused by the genus *Puccinia*, and also named black, brown and yellow rusts), powdery mildew (by *Mycosphaerella graminicola*), septoria (by *Septoria tritici blotch*) and Fusarium head blight (FHB). Considering that most of the trials have been conducted under natural infections and varieties could also appear tolerant for an escape mechanism, very interesting seem to be the varieties Antalis, Kanakis and Ramirez in Italy against leaf and yellow rust,

followed by other modern varieties like Claudio, Tirex, Marakas. For stem rust, instead, in addition to Marakas and Tirex, many others, in particular, from experimental trials carried out in Northern Italy in 2015, seem to be tolerant. In Morocco, the cv Faraj resulted in resistance to leaf rust. The best varieties in terms of powdery mildew resistance could be the cv Mario for North Italy and Anvergur, Daurur, Casteldoux and Heraclion for Central Italy, the last ones having also a good level of tolerance against leaf rust. Regarding tan spot, the best results were found for landraces Bidi, MG4482, MG4484, Amarelejo and Anafil, cultivated in Tunisia during two growing seasons. In that environment, landraces are generally more resistant to tan spot than cultivars, except for some cases, such as the cv Giorgio 448, which are classified as resistant. About FHB, no complete resistance was identified in durum wheat till now, as known in the literature. Nevertheless, Ramirez, Saragolla, Kanakis, or Claudio seem to adapt well to Central Italy during 2011–2012. The cultivars Saragolla and Ramirez, among others, appear to be also resistant to Septoria when evaluated in environments from South and Central Italy, whereas almost all varieties from the trial at Bou Salem (Tunisia) resulted in resistance to the disease (Ben M'Barek et al. 2022).

Regarding quality, we consider the protein content as the key factor influencing the manufacture of pasta and sodium dodecyl sulphate-sedimentation (SDS) volume as a key index to evaluate the gluten strength and, therefore, the end-use quality of durum wheat. In literature, durum wheat is reported to have a high protein content of around 15%. From our research, modern varieties like Massimo Meridio, Svevo, Aureo and Pietrafitta reached more than 16% protein content values. In particular, Pietrafitta showed a very high percentage (18%) when evaluated in Foggia in 2012. No information about this trait is available for landraces. Regarding SDS, as higher values resulted in better quality, the range was from 43 in RGT Rangodur (mean data from South of Italy) to 90 in Antalis (Foggia, 2017).

4.2 Bread wheat

Local wheat landraces have been grown for over millennia, assumingly accumulating a unique repertoire of genetic adaptations until the coming of varieties. There is a general agreement that modern high-yielding wheat varieties (with short stature) are more adapted to favourable growing conditions. In contrast, old cultivars and landraces have more stable yields under drought stress conditions due to their rich and complex ancestry representing vast variation in response to many diverse stresses, deriving many sustainable traits from their heritage.

Out of the 14,726 entries of the bread wheat database (D2.4), 808 rows were occupied by landraces and 13,920 by varieties. As landraces are genetically diverse breeding stocks that have been suited to their environments and farming methods, considerable variation among tested landraces was demonstrated on the basis of grain yield (GY) and some yield-related traits, such as Plant Height (PH), Thousand Kernel Weight (TKW), N spikes/plant, and they were classified into four groups from high-yielding to low-yielding (Rufo et al., 2021). Wheat landrace Sinai originated and grown in Egypt (Bahteem) in the 2016 and 2017 growing seasons, exhibited superiority for GY (12.7 ton/ha) and its components as N spikes/plant (48) and TKW (40.5 g). The second group involved two landraces, TRI 17938 and Solonetu Nou Xeixa, coming from France and Romania and tested in northeastern Spain under rainfed conditions for three consecutive seasons, 2016–2018, which were medium in GY (8.3 ton/ha) and

medium-high on average TKW (41.9 g), Harvest Index (HI 0.4) and PH (105.9 cm). The third group included seven landraces (Xeixa Tarragona, SVGB10195, Touzelle Belle Abec, TRI 10561, TRI 14173, TRI 16084, TRI 16900) showing GY on average 7.4 ton/ha. Finally, the fourth group, including most landraces, have yield values between 3 and 6.8 tons/ha.

In modern durum cultivars, the findings showed that grain yield greatly varied between 0.59 ton/ha to 14.36 ton/ha, and most of them were high-yielding varieties, with values ranging between 9 and 14 ton/ha (Rufo et al., 2021). Although yield values reported by Rufo et al. (2021) were representative of a wide set of landraces and varieties collected and adapted to different Mediterranean countries, in which a rise in temperature by 3–5 °C and a decrease in the annual rainfall by 25–30% have been found, some remarks to highlight are required. In fact, the field trials were conducted at Lleida (northeastern Spain) under rainfed conditions for three consecutive seasons (2016–2018). Moreover, the experiments followed a non-replicated augmented design with two replicated checks at a ratio of 1:4 between checks and tested genotypes and in 3.6 m² plots with eight rows spaced 0.15 m apart. So, even if the identification of genotypes that are able to maintain acceptable levels of yield stability in semi-arid environments is an important goal, the experimental conditions (*i.e.*, rainfed trials and field plots) explained the significant variability and the higher values of yield found in landraces and varieties respect to data reported in the literature for open field trials, equal to 1–3 ton/ha and 6–10 ton/ha, respectively. Compared to landraces, varieties exhibited significantly higher grain yield (GY) across environments, reflecting the effect of the Green Revolution. In fact, during the "Green Revolution", modern wheat was subjected to genetic selection aimed at maximizing yield and improving resistance of the plants, resulting in a reduction in height to about 70/80 cm. PH decreased passing from a 120–180 cm of landraces and old varieties to 70–90 cm of modern varieties after the introduction of the dwarfing genes from bread wheat. The selection imposed by breeders on plant height was due to the selection of cultivars well adapted to the Italian semi-arid conditions, where early maturity allows better tackling the drought season. Besides older, tall cultivars had low Harvest Index (HI, a proportion of total dry crop biomass growth, dry matter, that is harvested as grain) in comparison with the modern and short cultivars.

Regarding wheat disease, particularly *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *Tritici* is responsible for stripe rust, determining high grain yield losses. Shahin et al. (2024) analysed thirty-eight wheat genotypes grown in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate (northern region of the Nile Delta) during the three successive seasons, 2021–2023, finding in Misr 3 and Misr 4 a disease resistance with no outward symptoms of stripe rust infections or pustules. Moreover, Giza171, Gemmeiza10, Sids13, and Sakha93 demonstrated a moderately resistant (R to MR) infection type. On the other hand, three genotypes demonstrated a moderately resistant to moderately susceptible (MR to MS) infection type, namely Sakha94, Giza168, and Gemmeiza9. All the other genotypes included in the database (D2.4) were susceptible (S). The grains of resistant genotypes resulted also bolder and heavier.

As regards quality, proteins are the major determinants influencing the end-use quality and manufacturing of various wheat-based products. Mature wheat grains contain 8–20% protein. Landraces showed higher proteins (15.2 %, on average) when compared with modern cultivars (mean value 11.2 %, range 10.3% and 12.2%) for bread-making purposes. Instead, an ascending trend from landraces to modern varieties was observed for sodium

dodecyl sulphate-sedimentation (SDS) volume, which is considered a key index to evaluate the gluten strength of wheat and is linked to baking quality.

Al-Naggar et al. (2020) reported some yield-related and quality traits in two common varieties as Sakha 64 (an Egyptian cultivar) and Yakora Kojo (a drought-tolerant variety obtained from CIMMYT) grown in Gemmeiza, Gharbia Governorate, in 2016 and 2017 growing seasons. The experiment was conducted with 2 irrigation regimes, *i.e.* normal irrigation by giving the recommended number (five) of irrigations (sowing irrigation, the second one after 21 days and the next ones after every 25 days) and deficit irrigation by giving only two irrigations (sowing irrigation and the next one after 21 days) after which irrigation was stopped till the end of the season. Data on PH, N grains/spike and TKW were similar in both conditions, with mean values of 113 cm, 55.2 and 46.3 g. Regarding quality, the mean value of proteins was 13.9 %, more devoted to bread-making purposes. Considering data obtained in conventional management, reduced yield values were recorded in the varieties. As indicated by Tita et al. (2025), rainfed conditions with low nitrogen consistently resulted in lower yields, such as 2.0–3.0 t ha⁻¹, while combined irrigation (up to 240 mm) and high nitrogen rates (120–180 kg ha⁻¹) achieved yields as high as 7.5–9.0 t ha⁻¹. Notably, yields increased by over 50% when irrigation was paired with optimal nitrogen.

4.3 Barley

Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) is widely grown in semi-arid regions, even if it is also well adapted to the Northern regions, thanks to its resistance to cold stress. Its ability to grow in poor soils and withstand limited water availability is the basis of its importance in MENA countries. Barley serves multiple purposes, including human consumption, animal feed, and beer production. Given its hardiness and versatility, barley plays a crucial role in ensuring food security across different climatic conditions. Recent research efforts have focused on improving its genetic traits to enhance its resistance to abiotic and biotic stresses, such as heat, drought and fungal diseases, while also improving its grain quality for various uses.

In the database (D 2.4), out of 370 entries, 179 data points were available for grain yield for barley in 10 environments, for some of which two or three years of evaluation were available. A total of 128 cultivars were evaluated in different environments/ years and with differences in agronomic management. The general grain yield values ranged from 0.88 (in Turkey) to 9 (in Italy) tons per hectare. The highest values for grain yield were associated with greater rainfalls (661 rain mm were registered in 2015 at Perugia, Central Italy, where the highest values were recorded (Tomasi et al. 2019), or irrigated regime, with very low grain yield in drought environments or some environments in Egypt in which irrigation with saline water was applied (Ehab et al. 2021). Tazio was observed as a good cultivar for grain yield (4.7–7.2 tons per hectare) in two years of evaluation in Central Italy (L'Informatore Agrario), as well as Belgravia (Tomasi et al. 2019). Planet also showed good behaviour in terms of grain yield with consistent values in two very different environments: Ethiopia (4.11 tons per hectare) and Central Italy (6 tons per hectare). A very interesting cultivar is Martino, a high-yielding genotype in both Italy (6.70 tons per hectare) and Turkey (5.43 tons per hectare) in rainfed conditions (L'Informatore Agrario; Güngör et al. 2023). Known as an important yield component, thousand kernel weight (TKW) was considered in most studies here. This trait showed a great phenotypic variation, with values ranging from 23.1 to 59.3. Particularly interesting

were the cultivars KSU B101 and Giza 123, characterised by very high TKW (>56) and good grain yield (7.81 and 5.35 tons per hectare, respectively), when grown in Saudi Arabia (Elshafei et al. 2024).

For grain quality, a great phenotypic variation was observed for protein content, with values comprised between 8.6 and 16.6%, and a clear negative correlation with grain yield, as well as expected. In this range, cultivars such as Violetta and Yalin represent a good compromise between these two important traits (Tomasi et al. 2019; Akgun et al. 2023).

Morpho-phenological traits were also considered, as plant height, which was characterised by a large variation, with values ranging from 49 to 113 cm, with many of the best grain-yielding cultivars comprised between 80 and 100 cm. For heading, time values between 65 and 117 days were observed, with a shorter cycle being advantageous in grain yield in most drought conditions.

For reaction to fungal diseases, fusarium head blight (FHB) was considered in particular by Sakr et al. (2020). Disease incidence (type I) and disease severity (type II) were evaluated in adult plants of two cultivars, Arabi Aswad and Arabi Abiad, for 3 years and with 16 different isolates. Values ranging from 24 to 63% were observed for type I reaction, while values comprised between 19 and 51% were found for type II reaction, therefore, phenotypes of complete resistance or susceptibility were absent. Particularly interesting were the cases of isolates F3 and F27, for which both cultivars showed values of disease incidence and severity between 30 and 40%, therefore with a phenotype of moderate resistance. On the other hand, the isolate F2 revealed a contrasting behaviour, with Arabi Aswad characterised by a good level of resistance and Arabi Abiad showing a more severe effect of the disease.

5. Good Agricultural Practices for a modern wheat and barley cultivation in MENA countries

Good Agricultural Practices are defined by **FAO** as a "collection of principles to apply for on-farm production and post-production processes, resulting in safe and healthy food and non-food agriculture products, while taking into account economic, social and environmental sustainability" ([FAO - COMMITTEE ON AGRICULTURE \(17th Session\)](#)).

They consist of a comprehensive set of principles, regulations and technical recommendations applicable to production emphasizing agricultural production that does not harm the environment, prioritising human and animal health, protecting natural resources, ensuring traceability and sustainability in agricultural production, and provides a reliable supply of farms.

Four principles of GAPs apply to all scales of farming:

- 1) Economic viability: safety, quality, and nutritious agriculture products, improved health outcomes for consumers, the safety of farmers, and protection of natural resources due to less use of agrochemicals.
- 2) Food safety and quality aims at the reduction of:
 - Biological hazards: foodborne microorganisms, such as bacteria, viruses, and parasites.

- Chemical hazards: contaminated water or unsanitary handling practices, misuse of pesticides during production, or other chemicals after harvest.
 - Physical hazards: foreign bodies such as packaging from harvesting (wood, metal, etc.), foreign material collected during harvesting, residual soil, and stones found on fruits and vegetables.
- 3) Social acceptability barriers related to limited understanding, awareness, and knowledge of the application of GAP among producers and stakeholders and lack of price premium for GAP-certified, lack of infrastructure, management, socio-economic, institutional support, training, and skill, increased production costs required for labor and equipment.
 - 4) Environmental sustainability improved soil organic carbon, biological properties, and crop productivity, increased water retention, reduced soil erosion, increased carbon and nitrogen content, and enhanced soil physical and chemical properties

5.1 CEREALS: Durum Wheat, Bread Wheat and Barley

In the common language, the term wheat refers to several wheat species, which can be classified as bread or durum wheat. These plants belong to the genus *Triticum*, the subtribe Triticinae, the tribe Triticeae, and the Gramineae family, and their name honors the great Swedish naturalist Carl Linnaeus. Within this family, there are many other cultivated plants, such as corn, barley, rice, and rye, commonly known as cereals, in honor of the Latin goddess of agriculture, Ceres.

There are three species of wheat characterised by a base chromosome number of $x = 7$ and three ploidy levels: diploid $2n = 2x = 14$, tetraploid $2n = 4x = 28$, and hexaploid $2n = 6x = 42$. In the following table elaborated by CREA all details are reported.

Table10. Details on ploidy formula of different wheats.

	Species	Common name	Chromosome number	Genomic formula	Cultivated/Wild
Diploid species	<i>Triticum boeoticum</i>	Wild Einkorn wheat	$2n = 14$	$A^m A^m$	W
	<i>Triticum urartu</i>		$2n = 14$	$A^u A^u$	W
	<i>Triticum aegilopoides</i>		$2n = 14$	AA	W
	<i>Triticum monococcum</i>	Einkorn wheat	$2n = 14$	$A^m A^m$	C
	<i>Aegilops speltoides</i>		$2n = 14$	SS (BB/GG)	W
	<i>Aegilops caudata</i>		$2n = 14$	CC	W
	<i>Aegilops tauschii</i>		$2n = 14$	DD	W
	<i>Dasypyrum villosum</i>		$2n = 14$	VV	W
	<i>Secale cereale</i>		$2n = 14$	RR	C
Tetraploid species	<i>Triticum turgidum</i> ssp. <i>dicoccoides</i>	Wild emmer	$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u BB$	C
	<i>Triticum turgidum</i> ssp. <i>dicoccum</i>	Emmer wheat	$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u BB$	C
	<i>Triticum turgidum</i> ssp. <i>turanicum</i>		$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u BB$	C
	<i>Triticum turgidum</i> ssp. <i>turgidum</i>	Solid stem wheat	$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u BB$	C
	<i>Triticum turgidum</i> ssp. <i>carthlicum</i>	Persian wheat	$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u BB$	C
	<i>Triticum turgidum</i> ssp. <i>polonicum</i>	Polish wheat	$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u BB$	C
	<i>Triticum turgidum</i> ssp. <i>durum</i>	Durum wheat	$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u BB$	C
	<i>Triticum araraticum</i>		$2n = 4x = 28$	$A^u A^u GG$	W

	<i>Triticum timopheevii</i>		$2n = 4x = 28$	A ⁴ A ⁴ GG	W
Hexaploid species	<i>Triticum sphaerococcum</i>		$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBDD	W
	<i>Triticum vavilov</i>		$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBDD	W
	<i>Triticum macha</i>		$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBDD	W
	<i>Triticum spelta</i>	Spelt wheat	$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBDD	C
	<i>Triticum compactum</i>	Club wheat	$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBDD	C
	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	Common bread wheat	$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBDD	C
	<i>Triticum zhukovskiyi</i> (<i>T. timopheevii</i> / <i>T. monococcum</i>)		$2n = 6x = 42$	A ^m A ^m A ⁴ A ⁴ GG	C
	Tritopyrum (<i>D. villosum</i> / <i>T. durum</i>)		$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBVV	C
	Tritordeum (<i>H. chilensis</i> / <i>T. durum</i>)		$2n = 6x = 42$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBHH	C
	Triticale (<i>S. cereale</i> / <i>T. durum</i> or <i>aestivum</i>)		$2n = 6x = 42$ or $2n = 4x = 49$	A ⁴ A ⁴ BBRR or A ⁴ A ⁴ BBDDRR	or C

Among diploid wheats, in addition to *Triticum urartu*, *T. monococcum* is still cultivated, although to a lesser extent, although *T. aegilopoides*, its wild form, is more widely distributed. Hybrids obtained from the cross between these last two species are fully fertile, while hybrids between *T. monococcum* and *T. urartu* are completely sterile.

Among tetraploid wheats, *T. turgidum* and *T. timopheevii* are cultivated, and since hybrids between these two species are completely sterile, it can also be said that they are two distinct biological species. An ancient cultivated hulled wheat, *T. turgidum* ssp. *dicoccum*, has been almost completely replaced by *T. turgidum* ssp. *durum*, a completely naked wheat. *T. timopheevii* has no economic importance, while the wild forms of both species (*T. turgidum* ssp. *dicoccoides* and *T. timopheevii* ssp. *armeniicum* or *T. araraticum*) are widely distributed in the Fertile Crescent region.

T. aestivum and *T. zhukovskiyi* (a botanical curiosity) are among the hexaploid wheat found in cultivation. *T. aestivum* is of significant economic importance and, together with rice, represents the main source of food for humans. The following figure show the characteristics of spikes of different wheats from the wheat collection available at CREA.

Figure 12. Characteristics of spikes of different wheats from the wheat collection available at CREA.

The remains of cultivated emmer wheat (*T. turgidum* ssp. *dicoccum*), dated to 7.500 B.C., have been discovered in several archaeological sites in Syria (Zohary and Hopf, 1993), and the earliest naked forms of emmer seem to have originated from mutations of primitive emmer wheat.

Bread wheat comes from the Caspian Sea region in Iran (Dvorak et al., 1998). In this area, *Ae. tauschii* var. *strangolata*, the predominant species, evidently hybridised with cultivated emmer to give rise to *T. aestivum*. It is likely that several independent hybridization events occurred, leading to the gene pool of soft wheat (Talbert et al., 1998). The earliest cultivated soft wheat might have resembled *T. aestivum* ssp. *spelta*, discovered in Iran, from which naked forms were derived through mutation (McFadden and Sears, 1946). European spelt wheats may have secondarily originated from hybridization between *T. compactum* and *T. spelta* (Ohtsuka, 1998). It first appeared in Europe around the Bronze Age, while in Italy, the earliest wheat cultivations date back to around 7300-6500 BC in sites in Puglia (in the provinces of Foggia, Bari, Brindisi, Lecce, and Taranto).

The wheat plant comprises four main structures: root, stem, leaves, and spike. It has a fasciculate root system, formed by a bundle of roots arranged in a radial pattern around the stem, which penetrate about 70-80 cm deep; above the root is the stem, which bears 5-8 nodes and reaches a height of between 70 and 100 cm depending on the variety. Attached to the stem are the leaves, generally numbering 7-8. The leaf consists of two parts: the sheath and the blade. It ends with the spike, which is made up of flowers, kernels, and the spikelet. The most important phenological stages of wheat are germination, emergence, tillering, stem elongation (booting and heading), pollination and flowering, fertilization, and maturation.

PEDOCLIMATIC REQUIREMENTS

Wheat, although adaptable to various types of soil, prefers soils with good structure, medium texture, or clayey if water stagnation does not occur and the soil is rich in nutrients and organic matter, with a pH ranging from 6.5 to 7.8. Thermal requirements increase for the successive phenological stages: for germination and tillering, temperatures of 2-3°C are sufficient, 10°C for stem elongation, 15°C for flowering, and 20°C for maturation. During tillering, durum wheat can tolerate low temperatures (a few degrees below zero), but later, during stem elongation, a few degrees below zero can cause damage to the elongating internodes. Near flowering, temperatures below 0°C can cause flower death in the spike; also, sudden temperature increases beyond the seasonal average can compromise flowering and the proper filling of the spike. The grain-filling phase is favored by temperatures around 20-25°C; excessive temperatures during this phase reduce the accumulation of reserve substances in the grains and increase the risk of heat stress.

CROP ROTATION

The production of high-quality durum wheat is achieved within a crop rotation program that includes the use of soil-improving crops and/or soil fertility renewal, such as peas, broad beans, bitter vetch, lupine, chickling, lentils, chickpeas, vetch, sainfoin, forage crops, and herbaceous plants with leguminous species, as well as tomatoes, rapeseed, mustard, sunflower, beetroot, and other vegetables.

Renewal crops (e.g., tomatoes, beets, cauliflower, etc.) are excellent preceding crops for durum wheat because they improve the soil through deep tillage and abundant fertilization, including organic fertilizers, and help with good control of weeds. A potential factor to consider is the harvest timing of the renewal crop, in relation to the time available to prepare the land for sowing durum wheat. For high-quality production, durum wheat should not be cultivated following another autumn cereal (durum wheat, soft wheat, triticale, spelt, rye, barley, oats, emmer, millet, etc.) because the consecutive cultivation negatively affects the qualitative and quantitative aspects of the grain.

SEEDBED PREPARATION

Soil management and tillage techniques for seedbed preparation must aim to maintain the soil in good structural condition, preserving its organic matter content and fertility while also improving nutrient efficiency, promoting the penetration of rainwater and irrigation water, reducing water losses due to leaching, runoff, and evaporation, and preventing soil erosion. In recent years, the revision of tillage techniques has resulted in a significant reduction in the depth of tillage and a notable increase in the use of the direct seeding technique "no-till." In general, seedbed preparation tasks must be carried out with the aim of preventing potential erosive phenomena and soil degradation. To this end, interventions should be planned based on the soil type, topography, erosion risks, and the climatic conditions of the area. They should also help maintain soil structure and reduce compaction, allowing excess rainwater to drain away. Several tillage methods can be used without altering production levels:

- Minimum tillage with a harrow, disc or rotary at a depth of 10-15 cm
- Direct seeding (requires specific seeders)
- Reduced tillage to 25-30 cm depth
- Two-layer tillage, with a cracking layer at 40-60 cm, plowing at 20-25 cm and/or clod crushing
- Plowing to a depth of less than 40 cm followed by clod-breaking operations.

For successful "no-till" sowing, it is important to emphasise that it should be carried out with some advance compared to traditional sowing. To maintain soil structure, farmers must ensure the proper use of machinery. Tillage operations should be carried out under appropriate soil moisture conditions (in temperate state).

VARIETAL SELECTION

Using certified seed is essential, treated with products authorised by phytosanitary services and sold only by authorised suppliers. To achieve a good production of wheat or barley, it is important to choose the right variety and plan the purchase in advance of sowing. The seed must meet fundamental purity requirements (both varietal and free from foreign materials, especially weed seeds), germinability (health status and size of the kernels), ensuring optimal crop investment.

The choice of variety depends on environmental (pedoclimatic) and agronomic characteristics of where the crop is grown, with particular reference to the cultivation area, sowing time, type and fertility level of the soil, the availability of technical means in cultivation, and the quality of the product desired.

Specifically, the variety must have the following characteristics:

- I. high and consistent yield over time

- II. resistance to lodging and heat stress
- III. resistance to major physiological disorders
- IV. high protein content and good gluten index
- V. good hectoliter weight and high yellow index.

For plains and mid-hill areas, early and medium-early cycle varieties are preferred, while in mountainous areas, medium and medium-late cycle varieties are preferred, as they present lower risks of fungal infections. In areas with harsh winters, cold-resistant varieties should be chosen, while on poor soils, it is better to sow less demanding varieties in terms of nutrition or, better, those that more effectively process and translocate the few available elements.

Below are the main qualitative characteristics of wheat varieties to consider:

- **Yield Index:** It expresses the productive performance of a variety, with 100 being the field average. Yield indices above 100 indicate a varietal performance superior to the field average yield.
- **Hectoliter Weight (kg/hl):** It is largely determined by the conditions during the "seed filling" phase by the plant. In the judgment of processors, hectoliter weight represents the bulkiness of the kernel, which is considered a favorable ratio between endosperm (the useful part) and bran (the waste). Therefore, low hectoliter weight corresponds to low milling yield, a higher ash content, and, consequently, a dull pasta color.
- **Thousand Kernel Weight (g):** It is largely influenced by varietal characteristics and production conditions. It is related to the phenomenon of kernel shrinkage that occurs under climatic conditions.
- **Plant Height (cm):** this trait is determined at flowering by measuring the plants from the soil to the spike, excluding the awns.
- **Protein Content (% dry matter):** this is a parameter strongly influenced by the cultivation environment and agronomic practices (nitrogen fertilization). In general, there is an inverse correlation between yield and protein content. More than protein content, the quality of the proteins is important, as they give the pasta their cooking resistance, which is directly dependent on varietal characteristics.
- **Heading Date:** Expressed as the number of days from April 1, this coincides with the emergence of the spike from the sheath of the last leaf.

SEEDING

Seeding Time

In general, in the cereal-growing areas, the optimal seeding time is between early November and the first ten days of December, advancing in higher altitude areas and in north-facing fields and delaying in lower areas and more drought-prone regions. However, it varies significantly depending on rainfall and temperature.

Choosing the optimal seeding time, also in relation to weather conditions, ensures a better uniformity of seedling emergence, increased tillering, better control of weeds, a reduction in the establishment and spread of "foot rot", and less luxuriant plant growth. In the case of delayed sowing, it is recommended to use early-cycle varieties.

Seeding Method

Barley and wheat seeding is done using row seeders. Broadcasting is only allowed in exceptional cases where precision equipment is available to ensure uniform seed distribution and correct burial.

In the case of seeding on firm soil, specific machines with disc parts are used to make a vertical cut in the soil, and the seed is deposited at a depth of 3-5 cm through a collector. In the case of minimal or reduced tillage, combined seeders with rotary tools can be used to prepare the seedbed, and they are connected to normal seeders with a hopper or classic mechanical or pneumatic seeders, the same ones typically used after deep tillage.

Seeding Depth

Under typical conditions, the seeding depth for wheat is 3-5 cm. A deeper depth is recommended for soft, dry soils or in conditions of excessive cloudiness, while a shallower depth is preferred under the opposite conditions. Identifying the correct seeding depth, based on the environmental conditions (soil characteristics, moisture, etc.), will ensure prompt and uniform emergence of the plants. Generally, seeding too deep (>5 cm) reduces the tillering of the crop. In these cases, the final result will be a lower number of secondary tillers and fewer spikes per square meter.

Seeding Rate and Density

The amount of seed to be used can vary based on the pedoclimatic conditions of the cultivation area, soil fertility, and the chosen seeding time. A typical recommendation would be a seeding rate between 350 and 450 germinable seeds per square meter.

In particular, factors influencing the seeding rate are:

- 1) **Cultivation Area**
- 2) **Variety:** varieties with low tillering capacity require a higher seeding rate. The use of tall varieties requires a lower seed quantity.
- 3) **Soil Fertility:** soils with higher fertility and better water availability require higher seeding rates compared to poor and drought-prone soils.
- 4) **Seedbed Conditions:** excessive cloudiness, excessive presence of stones, and poorly executed refining operations require a significant increase in the seeding rate.
- 5) **Seeding Time:** delayed sowing requires a higher seed rate.

In general, both sparse and overly dense sowing should be avoided. In the latter case, an increase in plant size and a higher susceptibility to fungal diseases (e.g., powdery mildew) and lodging are often observed. Once the optimal density is determined, the seed quantity per hectare to be used will vary based on expected losses, seed germinability, and the weight of 1000 seeds of the chosen variety, and is calculated using the following formula: Sowing density (seeds/m²): (Plants at the end of winter (pp/m²) * 100) / (% germinability)

For easier evaluation of the seeding rate, based on the desired investment and the weight of 1000 seeds, the following table is elaborated by CREA.

Table 11. Schematic representation for easier evaluation of the seeding rate, according to the desired investment and thousand kernel weight.

Thousand Kernel Weight (g)		30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60
Sowing Density (seeds/m ²)	257	82	91	99	107	116	124	132	140	149	157	165
	300	90	99	108	117	126	135	144	153	162	171	180
	325	98	107	117	127	137	146	156	166	176	185	195
	350	105	116	126	137	147	157	168	179	189	200	210
	375	113	124	135	146	158	169	180	191	203	214	225
	400	120	132	144	156	168	180	192	204	216	228	240
	425	128	140	153	166	179	191	204	217	230	242	255
	450	135	149	162	176	189	203	216	230	243	257	270
	475	143	156	171	185	200	214	228	242	257	271	285
			Kg/hectare									

Density-based on seeding method and row spacing are:

I. **Single rows:** This method involves a spacing of approximately 18-20 cm between rows, with a seeding density of 350-450 seeds/m².

II. **Double rows:** This planting system is suitable when wheat is to be intercropped with a leguminous plant. The double-row system also allows the species to better tolerate water scarcity conditions. In this case, mechanised weed control is necessary through hoeing between the rows. The row spacing is 37-40 cm, and the plant spacing within the row is 6-10 cm, with a seeding density of 200-300 seeds/m². Although lower than single-row seeding, this method allows for more productive plants.

III. **Broadcast seeding:** This method is now rarely used, typically applied when precision seeding by rows is not possible, such as on steep terrain. The seeding density does not exceed 600 seeds/m², which allows for more effective control of weed development and compensates for lower germination rates.

IV. At CREA-CI in Foggia, a prototype of the "**SEMINBIO**" seeder has been developed (patent n. 281068, CREA Owner).

Figure 14. Schematic representation of the prototype SEMINBIO seeder developed by CREA.

It is a seeding device equipped with a system for adjusting the distance between rows to very small values (≤ 5 cm), which, for the same investment:

- Optimises the plant arrangement in space and ensures greater and quicker soil coverage
- Provides uniform seed distribution in space, as well as correct seeding depth
- Ensures better and faster soil coverage by the plants
- Increases the crop's competitive ability against weeds
- Reduces production costs and the consumption of phytosanitary products for conventional farms
- Improves the productive performance of the crop in both conventional and organic farming systems.

For example, if we consider a seeding density of 350 seeds per m^2 , a weight of 1000 seeds equal to 50 g, and a germination rate of 95%, the number of seeds to be distributed per hectare is $(50 \times 350) / 95 = 184$ kg/ha. Currently, the weight of 1000 seeds is not always indicated on seed packages, while the germination values reported usually show the minimum level required by legislation for marketing seeds (85%). In such cases, you can weigh 200 seeds and then multiply the weight by 5 to obtain the weight of 1000 seeds. Similarly, to calculate the actual germination percentage, it is sufficient to randomly take 100 seeds from the package, thoroughly moisten them with water, and store them between two sheets of absorbent paper in a warm, dark environment (around $20^\circ C$) for 3-5 days. At the end of the period, simply count the number of seeds with fully sprouted roots and shoots to determine the exact germination rate.

FERTILIZATION

A balanced supply of fertilising elements (Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium) in the right quantities and at the correct time of distribution is necessary to achieve satisfactory results in terms of yield and grain quality. The company must have information about the chemical-physical characteristics of the soil, which can be obtained through laboratory analysis. These analyses should be carried out every 5 years, with one analysis for every 5-10 hectares (depending on the size of the farm and the types of soil present), to check the soil's fertility and plan a proper fertilisation technique. Alternatively, instead of creating an analytical fertilisation plan, a simplified model can be adopted using the standard dose sheets provided below.

- **Timing and methods of fertilization**

PHOSPHORUS (P): Wheat has low phosphorus requirements, and if soil analysis shows a provision of at least 20 ppm of P_2O_5 , which is commonly found in soils with a medium texture or clayey soils, phosphate fertilisation could be omitted. The recommended dose is 50-70 kg/ha of P_2O_5 when necessary. Due to its low mobility in the soil, phosphorus fertilisation should be carried out during seedbed preparation, or in a localised form at sowing, or preferably, applied to more demanding crops before wheat (renewals, vegetables, pastures, etc.); this technical choice becomes essential when minimum tillage or direct sowing is planned for wheat.

POTASSIUM (K): Potassium is generally present in more than sufficient quantities in Italian soils, but if the analysis reveals a deficiency (less than 100 ppm of K_2O), it should be distributed during seedbed preparation or, preferably, applied to more demanding crops before wheat (beets, vegetables, oilseeds); this technical choice

becomes essential when minimum tillage or direct sowing is planned for wheat and barley. It should also be remembered that wheat has modest potassium requirements and a good cation exchange capacity, making it able to easily extract potassium from the soil. Generally, the K_2O supply varies depending on the soil's provision, ranging from 0 (high) to 120 kg/ha (scarce).

NITROGEN (N): Nitrogen fertilisation is a key element in wheat and barley cultivation to increase productivity. There is no single fertilisation method suitable for all situations, as the principles to follow in determining nitrogen doses and methods depend on several factors: varietal characteristics, climatic conditions and water availability, production and quality goals, amount of nitrogen present in the soil, intensity of organic matter mineralisation, the burial of crop residues (straw) from the previous crop, cost of fertiliser, and environmental aspects.

In Mediterranean areas, which are often characterised by potential early spring-summer drought and related risks of heat stress or inadequate water availability, assuming yields between 3 and 4.5 tons/ha, the average total nitrogen dose for the growing season should be around 120 kg/ha.

Therefore, it is essential to first examine the crop's needs, returns, and removals, then determine the amount of mineral elements to be applied based on soil analysis results. Another important factor is estimating the theoretical production that is expected to be achieved. Based on this production, a theoretical average absorption can be estimated (table 10).

Table 12_ Average absorption (kg/ha) of the main nutrients based on production in durum wheat.

Nutrient elements	Potential yield (t/ha)						
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Nitrogen (N)	54	82	109	136	163	190	218
Phosphorus (P_2O_5)	27	40	40	51	62	71	82
Potassium (K_2O)	20	30	54	67	81	94	108

It is evident that nitrogen fertilisation plays a significant role in wheat and barley fertilisation. Considering the high mobility of nitrogen in the soil, it is necessary to apply the total recommended dose in different stages, based on the crop's needs, in order to avoid both volatilisation of the element in ammoniacal form and leaching into groundwater. In all cases, it is important to consider that nitrogen absorption becomes very intense from the end of the tillering phase and increases exponentially during the stem elongation phase. For this reason, it is necessary to ensure the plant receives the correct amount of nitrogen during the "spike at 1 cm" stage, which corresponds to the beginning of stem elongation, a phase in which the plant defines the number of seeds per spike. The choice of fertiliser type must consider both soil characteristics (soil nature, pH, organic matter, and intrinsic soil fertility) and climatic data (temperature, rainfall, etc.). Special attention should be paid to new formulations, such as organic-mineral blends and slow-release nitrogen fertilisers, which ensure better synchronisation with the crop's growth and development stages. In particular stress situations for plants, foliar treatments with water-soluble liquid fertilisers and biostimulants can be applied.

PLANT PROTECTION AGAINST PESTS AND WEEDS

Particular attention should be given to fungal pests, whose control should primarily be done through seed treatment, preventing or limiting the development and spread of certain important diseases such as foot rot complex, smut (*Tilletia* spp), and wheat bunts (*Ustilago tritici*). Direct seed treatment in the seeds' hoppers is strongly discouraged. It is recommended to use pre-treated seeds. Through specific monitoring, special attention should be given to the development and spread of fungi that cause diseases (powdery mildew, rust, etc.) during the vegetative stages, as they can compromise both yield and grain quality.

Chemical means should only be used if pests reach the "action threshold" or if environmental conditions are favourable for the infection by a pathogen. When choosing plant protection products, the following must be excluded:

- those with risk phrases on the label specifically referring to carcinogenic, teratogenic, mutagenic effects, etc. (R40, R48, R60, R61, R62, R63, R68);
- those that are very toxic or toxic.

It is possible to use plant protection products composed of two or more active substances if they are included in the guidelines and the instructions on the label are followed.

Weed management should be integrated by combining preventive defence methods with chemical ones and by adopting a rational crop rotation strategy. Adopting correct crop rotation management allows for differentiated operations and favours the balance of weed flora. It is also advisable to carry out pre-emergence treatments for weed control in cases of direct sowing or when significant grass weed infestations occurred in the previous year, and the presence of dicotyledons and oats is expected to be low. However, it is important to manage the farm economically to apply specific solutions. Furthermore, different active ingredients should be used to avoid the issue of weed resistance.

When the weeds are known, targeted interventions can be carried out, and by choosing the appropriate timing, the herbicide's control power can be maximised. In many cases, adding additives can reduce the herbicide dosage. However, it is not advisable to apply dosages different from those indicated by the manufacturers.

In the environmental respect program, it is recommended to use:

- I. active ingredients with low persistence and solubility
- II. formulations with microencapsulated active ingredients and vegetable organic solvents
- III. recyclable containers or water-soluble bags
- IV. any other precaution regarding the environment.

According to the phenological stage of wheat, intervention times can be classified as follows.

EARLY STAGE: Corresponding to the 2nd-3rd leaf stage up to the beginning of tillering. In this case, the intervention is applied to poorly developed weeds, but the effectiveness may decrease depending on the more or less adverse climatic conditions for weed control.

CLASSIC: Corresponding to the stage from the start to the end of tillering. Products with a broader spectrum of action can be used in a period with more favourable weather conditions for optimising treatments. However, it is necessary to act promptly to avoid competition between the crops and weeds.

LATE STAGE: Corresponding to the end of tillering-2nd node stem elongation. Perennial dicotyledon weeds are eliminated with very low costs.

From an agronomic point of view, weeds are divided into two groups: grasses and dicotyledons. The grass group, commonly called narrow-leaved weeds includes species such as *Avena spp.*, *Bromus*, *Lolium*, etc. The dicotyledon group, commonly called broad-leaved weeds includes species such as the common poppy, horsetail, common fumitory, common chamomile, and the creeping thistle (*Cirsium arvense*), which is increasingly present in our wheat fields and difficult to control.

In any case, the crop should be monitored closely, always selecting the best product based on the existing infestation and not allowing weeds to overpower the wheat and barley and take away nutrients. The infestation can consist only of monocotyledon or dicotyledon species, or it can be mixed. The choice of using monocotyledonicides and dicotyledonicides, either alone or in combination, will depend on the infestation. It should be noted that separate use of products increases the effectiveness of the different active ingredients, so it is advisable to use them at the minimum doses indicated by the manufacturers. In the case of mixtures, it is recommended to use the molecules at the highest doses, up to the maximum indicated.

Figure 15 The sprayer machine for the distribution of herbicide products, at CREA-CI in Foggia.

IRRIGATION

In some North African countries, such as Egypt, it is essential to irrigate the crop during the growing season to achieve good production. The irrigation of wheat and barley plants in the field depends on several factors, including soil type, climate, and plant growth stage. However, the basic irrigation stages can be summarized as follows:

1. Germination Stage: irrigation immediately after planting (in the case of broadcasting).
2. Tillering Stage: occurs about 2-3 weeks after planting.
3. Vegetative Growth and Elongation Stage.
4. Flowering Stage (Heading).
5. Grain Filling and Development Stage.
6. Irrigation at the End of the Season: stopping irrigation a sufficient period before harvest.

The irrigation techniques used are flood irrigation, sprinkler irrigation and drip irrigation.

Additional Tips:

- Monitor Soil Moisture: soil moisture should be monitored regularly to determine the need for irrigation.
- Use Modern Irrigation Techniques: modern irrigation techniques, such as drip and sprinkler irrigation, can be used to increase water use efficiency.
- Avoid Over-irrigation: over-irrigation leads to problems such as root rot and the spread of diseases.
- Irrigate in the Early Morning or Evening: irrigation should be avoided during midday hours to prevent water loss due to evaporation.
- Flood Irrigation: the field is divided into strips with a width of 15-20 meters and a length not exceeding 75 meters for easy control of irrigation water and the absolute application of fertilisers in a fertiliser tank.

HARVEST

The harvest is now fully mechanised, using combines, which carry out, in a single pass, the cutting of the plant and the separation of the grain from the straw. The straw can be collected, pressed into bales or round bales, or plowed under (after nitrogen fertilisation to promote microbial decomposition).

The timing of the harvest varies, and temperature and atmospheric humidity are the two parameters that must always be considered, along with the soil conditions (understood as water-holding capacity), before performing the harvesting. The maturation period, and thus the harvest time, also varies depending on the vegetative cycle of the variety. In our latitudes, the harvesting period typically ranges from mid-June to the end of July and is carried out when the plant is close to full maturity, with a moisture content of around 13% in the grains. As latitude and altitude increase, as mentioned, the maturation period lengthens. Proper regulation of the combine harvester is also crucial. For durum wheat harvesting, the thresher speed should be adjusted to around 900 rpm, and an appropriate distance between the thresher and the counter-thresher should be maintained to minimize grain breakage.

STORAGE METHODS

Great care must be taken in cleaning the silos before storing the product: dead spots in the warehouses, conveyors and/or augers, ventilation structures, false bottoms, and all equipment used for handling the grains must be thoroughly cleaned.

The stored product should never exceed a moisture content of 14%. In extreme cases, grain drying may be necessary, although this involves significant budgetary costs. The wheat should be subjected to entomological checks, and generally, infestations should be visually assessed both when the product comes from the field and from other storage sites. Every 7 days, the stored mass should be checked: both infestation levels and

temperature increases should be assessed. There should never be any sign of mould odor, which is the primary indicator of product spoilage.

Special attention should be paid to pathogens that could develop during storage because attacking the grains can cause significant damage to both the product destined for food use and that used by the seed industry.

If the product is stored for a period of less than two months, no treatment is necessary, although the installation of traps for pests is always advisable. If intervention is needed for pest control, conservation techniques based on physical systems should be adopted: forced refrigeration, a controlled atmosphere.

6. Conclusions

This report represents a valuable resource as it gives very useful information on cereal varieties to be potentially cultivated in the Mediterranean area, a very stressful environment characterised by difficult climate conditions. The careful analysis of meteorological data from Italy and MENA regions contributed to knowing the trend and the distribution of parameters like temperature and rainfall across years, helpful to have a clear comprehension of climate change in the past and future. A list of protocols to be applied in such regions is of great importance as the right agronomic practices aim to ensure sustainable agriculture while minimising negative environmental impacts. Better choice of resilient varieties, efficient use of available water through the application of supplemental irrigation, and timing of sowing time are among the key factors that have the potential to combat adverse production conditions. Hence, the genotype with drought- and heat-stress tolerant traits and disease resistance coupled with the site- and soil-specific customised bundled agronomic solutions are needed to improve the resilience and sustainability of cereal production in the MENA region.

The best varieties in terms of disease resistance, yield and quality, as emerged by the database (D2.4), are represented below:

**BREAD
WHEAT**

<p>High yield: Canaletto, Filon, Solehio, Porticcio, Somtuoso cs High disease resistance: Filon, Solehio, Somtuoso cs High quality: Guerrino, Lancillotto, Aiace vst, Teorema</p>	ITALY
<p>High yield: TRI 17938, Solonetu Nou, Xeixa, Touzelle Belle Abec</p>	SPAIN
<p>High disease resistance: Altin Besak, Tosun 144 High quality: Bezostaya-1</p>	TURKEY
<p>High disease resistance: Misr3, Misr4, Giza171, Sids13, Sakha93 High quality: Sakha94, Yakora Kojo</p>	EGYPT

BARLEY

<p>High yield: Tazio, Belgravia, Planet, Martino High quality: Violetta</p>	ITALY
<p>High yield: Rabat 071 High quality: Assiya</p>	MOROCCO
<p>High yield: Martino High quality: Yalin</p>	TURKEY
<p>High disease resistance: Arabi Assan, Arabi Abiad</p>	SYRIA
<p>High yield: Giza123, KSUB 101</p>	SAUDI ARABIA

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